

Final Report

Introduction to the project

The Open Soil Atlas project aims to generate a biodiverse, self-sustaining and organically growing Soil Data Atlas, enriched by citizens working together to balance and heal the Earth. Supported by the ACTION Team and a wide network of experts and cooperators, the Feld Food Forest community developed an open-source co-learning centre for the local community of Berlin. It consists of a website presenting guidelines in a textual and infographic form to educate the public and raise awareness about soil quality and fertility and the correlation between healthy soil and healthy communities. The online material was then combined with a series of free workshops, where citizens were taught how to make observations, test the soil, interpret results and draw conclusions. Combined with GPS locations, data about soil quality and soil fertility were then uploaded in a digital entry form, which, in the long term, will generate a high-resolution soil quality map.

Our findings aim furthermore to provide policymakers and urban ecology initiatives with indicators as to which areas are best suited for urban agricultural purposes and which require remediation activities.

The entire research and data collection process will then be replicated and expanded worldwide, in order to engage different communities and spread the analysis to new and different sites all over the world. The project builds on the Feld Food Forest citizen initiative and is promoted by its community.

The Feedback Loop

For the development of Open Soil Atlas we adopted the Feedback Loop approach. A feedback loop is the part of a system in which some portion (or all) of the system's output is used as input for future operations. Each feedback loop has a minimum of four stages. During the first stage, input is created. During the second stage, input is captured and stored. During the third stage, input is analyzed and during the fourth stage, the insight gained from analysis is used to make decisions.

Feedback was collected and elaborated on a monthly basis, in line with our project plan and the milestones to achieve.

Beginning of the activities

The first month (March 2021) served as a starting point for the research and development of our tools, while defining specific strategies for engaging the public.

Design of the research

After extensive research about the state of the art, the existing data about urban soil (e.g. Umweltatlas Berlin) and similar citizen science initiatives in the world (e.g. LandPKS), we defined our research goals and the structure for data collection. We developed a soil testing protocol, which would allow us to collect a wide range of information about the quality and fertility of the soil in specific locations around the city. The data collected move from the satellite level (GPS location), down to the earth (land use, anthropogenic impact, humus layer erosion) and below the earth (biological activity, color, soil profile, texture and pH).

In general, gathering data about the soil is challenging, mostly when it's about measuring what's below the surface. Academics might not have the capacity to collect such a comprehensive set of information about the soil at a very high resolution level. This is where citizen science becomes a very powerful tool, in order to collect data and gather information about the carbon storage potential of the soil and the availability of space for urban gardening.

Development of the tools

During the first month, we developed the first beta version of our tools that we use for training citizens and collecting the data. They are strongly interconnected and dependant on each other.

Virtual co-learning center

The virtual co-learning center is the place where we collect, generate and share knowledge about the soil. It consists of a website presenting guidelines in a textual and infographic form to educate the public and raise awareness about soil quality and fertility and the correlation between healthy soil and healthy communities.

In the "Overview of tests" page, all the different tests for examining the soil are explained in detail. For every test, the explanation structure indicates the level of difficulty, the data type, the meaning and importance of the data, the method for collection, the duration of the experiment, evaluation parameters, the toolkit and pictures/videos. Infographics are adopted as an important tool to train participants. A specific page is also designed to walk people through the upload of the data on Epicollect.

Workshops

The online material was then combined with a series of free workshops, where citizens were taught how to make observations, test the soil, interpret results and draw conclusions.

The first beta version of the workshop happened at the end of the first month. The workshop was an opportunity for participants to get to know the project more closely and to better understand the soil testing protocol. Online, we walked participants through our virtual co-learning center, brainstormed about the importance of the soil and how we interact with it.

The workshop was also the moment for us to present our project to the public, get visibility and start practicing digital educational skills.

Epicollect

After exploring the state of the art IT practices for data collection in citizen science, we selected Epicollect as the most suitable for our case. Being a domain specific app, it will help us to be part of a bigger community and, also, our data will have more impact.

According to the soil testing protocol, we developed the first version of our project in Epicollect. Data were supposed to be uploaded together with pictures, in order to give us the possibility to check the quality of the collected information. The entry form would walk citizens through the experiments and help them draw conclusions about some specific characteristics of the soil.

Communication, Outreach and Networking strategy

Communication with the public is a core aspect for the engagement of citizens. That mostly followed two main channels: communication on social media, outreach and networking with existing and new potential partners and cooperators.

Vision, mission and aims were first clearly defined through an extensive co-creation process. We defined our editorial plan for publishing on social channels and started collecting graphics and pool images to use for initial posts on FFF Instagram, Facebook and Twitter; Youtube channel. The social media strategy throughout the project, aimed at combining information about the soil with the invitation to take part in our trainings and getting engaged in a collective mapping of the Berliner soil.

Beside that, the outreach and networking team developed a strategy to ensure the engagement of all the stakeholders potentially impacted by our project. We identify stakeholder groups and specific strategies to engage all of them in the development of the project. After analysing the potential barriers that participants might face, we developed an action plan to ensure EDI (equity, diversity & inclusion) and geographical coverage.

Evaluation Phase - feedback collection - feedback processing

An evaluation phase, combined with the collection and processing of feedback, was carried out at the beginning of every month (starting from April, until July), as a milestone of our project plan.

This helped us to constantly evaluate our approach and progressively improve our tools and strategies. Through a learning-by-doing process, we managed to improve our activities every month and readapt them to the needs and feedback of all the actors involved.

Where does feedback come from?

Feedback was collected from all the actors involved in and impacted by the development of the project. The engagement of the widest public became central in order to make our project accessible to everybody and meet the needs of the public.

Feedback was collected from:

- OSA team members (internal feedback)
- Users and participants
- Cooperators, partners and supporters
- Policy makers
- ACTION Team

Each one of these groups impacted differently on the project. Users' opinions and questions allowed us to understand the usability and understability of our tools. Feedback from participants gave us the possibility to shape our educational material to different levels of knowledge, to understand what was not clear and how to make it simpler, in order also to guarantee the quality of the data. It allowed us to understand what motivates people to engage in citizen science and their expectations. Through the motivational questionnaire, we also collected information about the perceived inclusiveness and equity of the project and suggestions about how to make the activities accessible to a wider public.

Cooperators, partners and supporters were also a central contribution to the development of Open Soil Atlas. They allowed us to share experience with similar projects and explore potential collaborations. They gave us suggestions about how to improve, how to ensure the quality of the data, supporting us in the development of the entire system and improving the data collection strategy. The contribution from universities and the academic area played a very important role in ensuring reliability and truthfulness of the research process. Eco-initiative (e.g. community gardens) gave also very interesting input about the challenges that they constantly face (e.g. to have the right to stay in the area, to get access to water, etc.). It helped us to understand their needs and how we can support, by scientifically proving their impact on the environment and the society, while generating ecosystem services (CO₂ storage, regulation of underground water, recreational services).

Very enriching was also the discussion with a representative from the Senate Department for the Environment, Transport and Climate Protection and the Department of Open Space Planning and Urban Greening. The outcome of this dialogue was very interesting for the further development of the project and the understanding of the importance of connecting with public institutions and policy-makers. It helped us to understand the needs of the public and how we can support (provide useful data and information), while setting the basis for cooperation between the civic society and public institutions (for further insights, see the 3°

milestone's report). That also gave us the possibility to understand the strategy and plans of public institutions for the regeneration and decontamination of urban soil and what our role could be in this regard.

How is feedback collected?

Following the monthly structure of our project plan, an internal plenum meeting for the OSA Team was planned at the beginning of every month. This was the moment to update other sub-teams about the progress and reflect about how things went during the month. We collected feedback from the team, analysed what went well and what went wrong and defined action plans in order to reach KPIs and deliverables of the following month.

Feedback from users and participants were collected during the workshops. At the end of each workshop there was a moment when participants could share (even anonymously, if online) what they liked about the workshop and what should be improved. During offline workshops, it was also our responsibility to observe participants' reactions and collect pending questions and doubts. The motivational questionnaires have also been a very important tool to collect feedback and suggestions about the inclusiveness and equity of our project.

Feedback from external cooperators and supporters was collected during meetings or reports from them. They were then directed to the specific sub-team and elaborated; all this input was collected and served as inspiration and starting point for further developments.

How is feedback elaborated?

Every feedback was collected and analysed in a specific table, where action(s) to be taken and a responsible person (or team) were identified. This material is openly available in our monthly reports.

Outcome and examples

Being part of the project plan and the budget, the feedback analysis got a full implementation for the development of the workshops (mostly for the online activities - how to make it interactive and catchy, even missing the face-to-face interaction). Here some examples of the undertaken activities and the consequent improvements: the length of the workshop has been reduced through a revision of the structure, in order to fit the attention span of participants (introduction of breaks and physical activities during the workshop); technical problems were solved by switching to a more less CPU consuming video call tool; introduction of offline workshops beside the online ones, in order to provide hands-on demonstration of the tests (as asked from participants); agenda and tools for soil testing were shared beforehand, in order to align participants' expectations to the content of the workshop and allow them to better follow the explanation.

The outreaching strategy also went through constant review (mostly internally). Target groups are different and different channels fit to the specific group. For example, we didn't get responses when gardeners were contacted per email, while it was much easier to get in contact with them through phone calls or using a pre-existing connection. What was mostly important was to build trust and highlight mutual benefits of a potential collaboration. Enlarging the network and establishing different connections is also a very important factor, which with time has become easier. If at the beginning it was difficult even to be hosted as workshop givers, now we are receiving a lot of invitations, mostly by word of mouth and thanks to the trust that we managed to establish. The communication language was also a critical point, being German much more effective when talking with the local community.

After continuous input and feedback about the entry form on Epicollect, a comprehensive feedback came from one of the participants and was the basis for a new version of the entry form, which is being tested by users at the moment and will be officially adopted for the post-accelerator phase. More explanations and details were added, in response to participants' questions, doubts and mistakes (data quality check). A new test has been added thanks to the suggestion from an expert.

Internally, while reviewing the educational and training potential of our tools (virtual co-learning center and workshop), we recognized the need to have an user manual that can be printed and brought on site to guide participants during the testing procedure. This is a reflection of what has been developed on the virtual co-learning center. The majority of the information still is available only online, but the user manual is an important tool to make the soil testing easier on site. More infographics and visual explanations were then introduced on the digital platform.

The motivational questionnaire was also an important tool to collect information about the inclusiveness of our project. Main insights were the need to translate the tools in German, to involve the local community, the possibility to connect with other initiatives working with minorities in order to engage them in the activities (otherwise, very difficult to reach) and the possibility of sharing tools among participants (sharing economy to enhance participation possibilities).

Citizen Engagement and Motivation

The original idea assumed that our role would have been only to generate clear guidelines and instructions about how to carry out the tests and participants would have then uploaded the data independently. However, after three online workshops, participants collected only three samples by themselves. Not meeting our KPIs, we had a reflection about what the problem could be:

- the soil testing protocol is quite long and might be challenging for people with no experience with the soil. The combination of the virtual co-learning center with the practical activity might also be challenging (technical problems of navigating on Internet with the phone, on the field and with dirty hands)

- people were not feeling confident to carry out the testing activity with no mentoring
- the data quality check of these data also showed that participants would have needed more trainings and mostly more hands-on demonstration of the testing activities
- lack of motivational factors.

The original strategy to engage citizen scientists and motivate them to participate has then been reviewed. The first intervention was the introduction of an offline moment after the online meeting (when the lockdown situation allowed that), as asked by participants. Still, the data set was slowly growing. The question then was how to inspire motivation and make participants feel comfortable enough to take the initiatives and carry out their own testing activities.

We decided to invest energies in incentivizing sociality and empowerment of participants. We started going massively on the street and having weekly appointments (2 or 3 times a week) to collect samples and train participants. We called these small, spontaneous events "soil meetups", to highlight that they were informal, spontaneous events, which offer people the possibility to meet up and share knowledge, experiences and curiosity. On the other side the so-called "soil ambassador" strategy was aimed at empowering participants, making them active mentors of newcomers and giving them the opportunity and the practice to train other people: spreading out circles of knowledge.

Social aspects turned out to be a main motivational factor. The opportunity to increase skills and co-learn, while meeting new people, establishing a community of common interests (yet not excluding people from different background or with a not so close relationship with the topic), getting an active role in knowledge sharing, while making a contribution to science turned out to be the main motivational factor that leads to engage in such initiatives.

This process gave us input to introduce gamification in the data collection process: if someone joins a practical training at least twice, he/she becomes a soil ambassador and receives a waterproof user manual (potentially also a toolkit for soil testing). Then, you are trained and equipped to test independently and train other people. That also guarantees the control of the collected data (training and proper equipment) and should increase the chances that people test by themselves.

Collected data

The collection of data intensified during the last two months, thanks to the soil meetups and the soil ambassador strategy. At the end we managed to have 77 entries in our database, with a partial coverage of the city (the western and more peripheral areas of the city have been more difficult to reach). More insights about the data will be presented in the final paper.

A parallel project of mapping street greenery in a central area of the city (Donaustrasse, Neukolln) has started and added 44 entries in a separate database. This activity has been

carried out for an external research project, in collaboration with Open Soil Atlas and one of the participants. The research aims at showing the impact of people taking care of these green spaces on the street, while analysing the motivation of people to transform small pieces of soil in living gardens. We are in contact with some of these actors and have already conducted some interviews. Using GIS techniques, the collected data will then be combined with other existing data (about vegetation, water drainage, etc.) and generate a map of the street, which will show the correlation between the activities carried out and the quality of the soil.

Further steps

The project has been designed with the intent to be replicable everywhere in the world. The idea for the future is to develop a package of replicable tools and guidelines about how to develop the same idea in other places. We want to give people guidelines about how to engage citizens in a collective effort of mapping and regenerating the soil in their cities, readapting the tools to specific social contexts and types of urban soils. We have already been listed as a potential cooperator in an application for fundings from the Humboldt University, aimed at applying Open Soil Atlas's schemes in Rio de Janeiro. Other expressions of interest came from Chile and we expect more to come in the future.

The scalability of the project has also been a core theme of the discussion during the last six months. Participants, cooperators and policy makers were pointing out the need of assessing soil contamination, if we want to vision and design edible landscapes in the city. During the acceleration period we didn't have capacity to move so far, but if this is the need, we aim at meeting it in the short future. We want to investigate citizen science practices for assessing soil contamination and develop different soil testing protocols for different users. Assessing soil contamination would require more money, the availability of a laboratory and some chemical analysis. Support from the university would be central for that.

We also want to better develop the tools that we designed during the last six months. We want to explore new apps or develop our own app for data collection, which would ideally allow us to condense in one space all the information and guidelines needed for soil testing (e.g. pictures, link, surveys, etc.).

In the long term we aim at developing a digital soil academy, where experts, citizens and practitioners of any kind come together to collectively build up soil regeneration competences. Notion, the platform we use for project management and the virtual co-learning center is a perfect tool for co-creation. We have already developed co-creation techniques and we aim at being a model project for bigger communities, inspired on sociocracy, permaculture ethics and the theory methodology, to inspire co-creation at different levels.